

Fluorescence Excitation Spectra of Different Fractions of Humus

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Fluorescence spectra of humic, hymatomelanolic and fulvic acid fractions of organic matter from Palampur, Chinsura, Dehra Dun, Darjeeling and Jodhpur soils were measured in aqueous solutions as well as in different solvents. The emitting radiation was fixed at 520 $m\mu$, and the fluorescent radiations at different wavelengths were recorded in terms of microammeter reading.

The fluorescence spectra of sodium humate, hymatomelanate and fulvate show maximum at 470 $m\mu$ in aqueous solution. This maximum remains unaltered in the residue after hydrolysis with 6N HCl. It may be noted that the electronic absorptions of all these materials are non-specific and decrease monotonously with wavelength.

The spectral maximum is shifted to different extents in different solvents. Thus in ether, pyridine, acetone and D.M.F. the maximum shifts to 370 $m\mu$, whereas in most of the alcohols the maximum is shown at 400 $m\mu$. In mixtures of solvents the maximum appears to be influenced by their composition.

The fact that the maximum appears only when the solutions are extremely diluted suggests that the extinction coefficient of the fluorescing species is very high.

Humic and fulvic acids isolated from diverse soil types exhibit visible fluorescence when excited by light of proper frequency. This fluorescence property has been utilised by a number of investigators^{1,2,3} to ascertain the progress of fractionation by chromatographic methods. Recently, one important finding⁴ has been made in the chemistry of soil organic matter which relates to the well-defined fluorescence emission spectra of humic, hymatomelanolic and fulvic acids. All fractions exhibit green fluorescence with emission maxima appearing in the region of 500–540 $m\mu$. The fluorescent radiations at different wavelengths have been recorded using a fixed exciting radiation of wavelength 365 $m\mu$. Since the nature of the emission spectra of all the acids was very similar, they inferred that these acids are more or less similar, probably representing the intermediate stages of a polymer series.

It is true for a great many substances that the fluorescence efficiency is independent of the exciting frequency. If, therefore, the total fluorescence intensity at a fixed wavelength is plotted against the frequency of the exciting light, the resulting fluorescence excitation spectrum will resemble the molecular absorption spectrum of the substance. This supposition was proved experimentally by a number of investigators using several dyes. A small shift of the emission curve towards longer wavelength was usually found. This supposition remains experimentally unrealised in the case of humic, hymatomelanolic and

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fulvic acids as the electronic absorptions are found to decrease continuously with increase in wavelength. A violation of this mirror-image relationship suggests that the fluorophores in humic acids are present in extremely small concentration so that they are sufficient to excite fluorescence but not absorption.

The present study attempts to obtain the molecular absorption spectra in terms of fluorescence excitation spectra and to investigate fluorescence property as a possible means of characterising humic, hymatomelanic and fulvic acids. In addition, the effects of changing the dielectric constant of the solvent, of using mixed solvents and of acid hydrolysis on the fluorescence emission spectra have been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

For the present investigation, one type of soil each from Palampur, Chinsura, Dehra Dun, Darjeeling and Jodhpur has been selected. The organic matter contents of the soils as determined by the method of Walkley and Black vary from 0.26 to 5.50%.

The humus from surface layer of the samples was extracted with 0.5*N* Na₂CO₃. The humic, hymatomelanic and fulvic fractions studied here were obtained by the usual procedure from this extract. The fulvic acid was converted into its barium salt, a form in which it was relatively more stable⁵ and humic and hymatomelanic acids were converted into their sodium salts for measurements of their fluorescence spectra. The dried sodium salts, barium salts and the acid forms were dissolved in different solvents by shaking and trituration and filtered. The filtrates were used for measurements. The residues remaining after 6*N* HCl hydrolysis of humic, hymatomelanic and fulvic acids in a sealed tube at 100° for 24 hours were also subjected to fluorescence measurements. The acid insoluble residues were separated from the hydrolysates by filtration, washed with distilled water and converted into sodium form as usual. The solvents such as, acetone, ether, pyridine, ethanol, methanol, *n*-butanol, *n*-propanol, isopropanol and dimethylformamide (D.M.F.) were distilled and properly purified prior to their use.

The fluorescence measurement was made in a Farrand Spectrofluorometer provided with a high pressure xenon arc lamp. The emitting radiation wavelength was fixed at 520 m μ . The sample was taken in a fused quartz cell of 1 cm thickness. The fluorescent radiations at different wavelengths were recorded directly in terms of microammeter reading.

RESULTS

Humic, hymatomelanic and fulvic acids are weakly fluorescent as evident by the necessity of using a large slit (1 mm.). It has been observed that in addition to Rayleigh scattering, there exists, to a very much smaller extent, a form of scattering at a wavelength of about 450 m μ called Raman scattering. This Raman scattering has been observed with all the solvents used and its essential nature was independent of the incident light. The concentrations of the sodium salts and acid forms which easily dissolved in water were kept at 3 mg/100 ml. In comparison, small amounts of these substances were soluble in organic solvents. Since in the present investigation, we have utilised the fluorescence

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property only to characterise different fractions of soil humus in a qualitative sense, their exact concentrations in the non-aqueous solutions have not been determined. It was, however, assured that the solutions were sufficiently dilute for obedience to Lambert-Beer Law. The fluorescence excitation spectra which were recorded in terms of microammeter reading have, however, been drawn in terms of intensity of emitted radiation taking it equivalent to the microammeter reading. Moreover, to prevent the overlapping of excitation curves the intensity scales have been suitably altered.

The fluorescence excitation spectra of sodium humate and fulvic acids from Palampur, Chinsura, Dehra Dun, Darjeeling and Jodhpur soils and sodium hymatomelanate from Palampur, Dehra Dun and Darjeeling soils in water are shown in Figs. 1, 2 and 3a respectively, the maxima appearing in all the cases at $470\text{ m}\mu$. The variation of pH of the solution has no effect on the nature and position of the fluorescence excitation spectra. Acid hydrolysis has also no effect on fluorescence property of humic, hymatomelanic and fulvic acids, since the non-hydrolysable residues of these humic fractions exhibit the same fluorescence maxima at $470\text{ m}\mu$ (only one of the curves is shown by broken line in Fig. 1.).

The influence of the solvent on the exact spectral location of the fluorescence bands has been a matter of discussion for a long period. It has been suggested⁶ that the colour of the fluorescence shifts continuously from violet to red with increasing dielectric constant of the solvent as in the case of dimethylnaphtheturhodine. Other examples can easily be

7. P. Pringsheim, Fluorescence and Phosphorescence, 1949, Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York.

found, however, which seem to prove exactly the contrary. According to results published by Sheppard (Pringsheim⁷, p. 400), the absorption bands of a great many dyes are shifted quite regularly toward greater wavelengths with decreasing index of refraction of the solvents, as long as only solvents of the same polarity are used. It might be justified to assume that this rule holds also for the fluorescence bands, although no actual measurements are at hand. It is another question whether the rule can be applied to other types of dissolved organic compounds.

The effect of varying the dielectric constant of the solvent on the nature and position of the fluorescence excitation spectra was studied using sodium humate, sodium hymato-melanate and barium fulvate from Palampur soil only. Some of the curves have been given in Fig. 3b and Fig. 4 and the emission maxima are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Solvent	Dielectric constant	Sodium humate	Sodium hymato-melanate	Barium fulvate
		λ_{max} in $m\mu$	λ_{max} in $m\mu$	λ_{max} in $m\mu$
Ether	4.37	370	370	370
Pyridine	8.08	370	—	—
Acetone	12.40	370	370	370
<i>n</i> -butanol	17.10	320 and 370	—	—
<i>iso</i> -propanol	18.30	400	400	400
<i>n</i> -propanol	20.10	400	400	400
Ethanol	24.30	400	400	400
Methanol	32.63	400	400	400
D.M.F.	36.80	370	370	370
Water	78.54	470	470	470

TABLE 2

Sodium humate in mixed solvents

A) 10% w/w of water in	Emission maximum in $m\mu$	Remarks
Ether	370	Excitation spectrum is of a flat nature.
Pyridine	370 and 470	370 and a weak 470 for concentrated solution and only 370 for very dilute solution.
Acetone	370 and 470	-Do-
<i>n</i> -butanol	320-330 and 370	A shoulder in the region 320-330 and a maximum at 370.
<i>n</i> -propanol	400 and 470	A sharp 470 maximum for concentrated solution and weak 400 and 470 for dilute solution.
Ethanol	400 and 470	-Do-
Methanol	400 and 470	-Do-
B) 10% w/w of ether in ethanol.	370 and 400	Very weak 400 and sharp 370.
C) 90% w/w of ether in ethanol.	370	Sharp.
D) 10% w/w of ether in methanol.	370 and 400	A weak 370 and a weak 400 for concentrated solution and only a sharp 370 for dilute solution.
E) 10% w/w of ether in butanol.	320-330 and 370	A shoulder in the region 320-330 and a sharp 370.

DISCUSSION

Humic, hmatomelanic (both in the form of sodium salts) and fulvic acids from all the soils in water exhibit fluorescence with emission maxima at $470\text{ m}\mu$ in their fluorescence excitation spectra which are more or less identical. This observation leads to a conclusion

that humic, hmatomelanic and fulvic acids are not independent groups of humic compounds, but are similar substances, probably representing the intermediate stages of a polymer series. The difference in the intensity of observed fluorescence may be due to the concentration variation of the fluorescing group in these substances.

Although the exact nature of the fluorescing group has not been clarified from the present investigation, the fluorescence property itself suggests the presence of either (a) an aromatic nucleus substituted by at least one electron-donating group or (b) a conjugated unsaturated system capable of high degree of resonance in humic and fulvic acids⁴. The former view is supported by the isolation of a number of aromatic compounds from the oxidative degradation products of humic acids.

The shape and position of the fluorescence excitation spectrum bear an approximate mirror-image relationship to that of the low frequency absorption band of the substances.

It is, therefore, expected that the absorption spectra of sodium humate, sodium hymatomelanate and fulvic acids in water will exhibit a maximum at about 470 $m\mu$. This expectation remains experimentally unrealised. The absorption spectra of all these acids are non-specific and the electronic absorptions are found to decrease continuously with increasing wavelength.

The effect of varying dielectric constant of the solvent on the position of the excitation spectra was studied in the case of sodium humate, sodium hymatomelanate and barium fulvate from Palampur soil only. It has been observed that the variation in the dielectric constant of the solvent has some effect on the position of the fluorescence excitation band suggesting that the fluorogens become dielectrically polarised. The excitation curves in ether, pyridine, acetone and D.M.F. show a maximum at 370 $m\mu$, probably representing the aggregation of humic, hymatomelanic and fulvic acids in those media through hydrogen-bonding. Most of the excitation curves in different alcohols show excitation maxima at a wavelength of 400 $m\mu$, excepting that in *n*-butanol which has got two peaks at 320 $m\mu$ and 370 $m\mu$.

The problem, is, of course, of a different kind if the nature of the dissolved molecules is altered by a reaction with the solvent. Such reactions may consist either of a change in the state of ionisation or in the formation of a new compound. For some experiments, the extracts with different solvents were vacuum dried and redissolved in D.M.F. and their

spectra were again observed, all of which show the same maxima as that in the original solvents, with only a small alteration in the excitation curve taking place. This may be accounted for by assuming that the solvents originally employed extract different substances which retain their character in D.M.F. However, it may be questioned why the original humic acid when studied in D.M.F. did not show similar spectra. This point needs further investigation.

The non-hydrolysable residues from all the fractions in water show emission maxima at a wavelength of $470\text{ m}\mu$ —a fact which indicates that fluorogens responsible for fluorescence have not originated from the amino acid (which is known to be present in proteins) moieties of the substances investigated.

A peculiarity observed in the present investigation is that some of the solutions do not apparently obey the Lambert-Beer Law, i.e., the amount of light transmitted does not depend on the concentration besides the thickness of the layer. It is evident from Fig. 5 that in the excitation curve (1) no maximum becomes noticeable, whereas after one-fourth and one-tenth dilutions of (1), the maxima appear in both the cases at $370\text{ m}\mu$, the latter being sharper. It may, therefore, be assumed that the fluorogen responsible for the fluorescence has a high extinction coefficient. In fact, while studying the fluorescence spectra sufficiently dilute solutions were used in order to ensure that the Lambert-Beer Law was obeyed.

Some fluorescence spectra of sodium humate were also studied in mixtures of two solvents one of which was present in 10% w/w. Two sets of data given in Table 2 (some of the graphs are also shown in Fig. 6) can be distinguished; the one refers, in column 1, to seven solvent mixtures containing 10% w/w of water in a nonaqueous solvent, the remaining set of four contains 10% w/w of a nonaqueous solvent in another, of which ether is one.

It is shown in Table 1 that in water the emission maximum occurs at 470 $m\mu$ for humic, hymatomelanic and fulvic acids, whereas in ether, pyridine, acetone, butanol and D.M.F. this is at 370 $m\mu$ and that in *n*-propanol, isopropanol, ethanol and methanol at 400 $m\mu$. When water is added to the extent of 10% w/w to the first group of solvents (except D.M.F.) the emission maximum is also at 370 $m\mu$ as it is so in the pure solvents, but in the case of pyridine and acetone the weak fluorescence maximum at 470 $m\mu$ is observed showing the influence of water. Similarly, in the second group of solvent mixtures, along with the 400 $m\mu$ maximum a 370 $m\mu$ maximum also appears, which is characteristic of ether. Ether seems to dominate over the other solvent, and the intensity of fluorescence appears to become greater as the proportion of ether is increased. The appearance of a shoulder at 320–330 $m\mu$ in addition to the sharp 370 $m\mu$ maximum in the ether-butanol mixture, is perhaps a modification of the peak observed in butanol alone.

The study presented above indicates that further work is needed along this line in order to fully understand the nature of the phenomenon of fluorescence observed in soil humus.

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